

INNOVATIONS AT DEPED

By: Jeddah P. Valencia
Teacher II BNHS SHS

While we are at the digital age, learners have now a very diversified way of learning especially those learners that have resources to afford and access those opportunities at hand. For many, it has been helpful but for some, it is still a dream to catch. As a teacher in Senior High School, we saw how learners hardly catch up on subjects that require a use of innovative tools and digital gadgets that may help them lessen their workload and may ease their burden to some areas that require technology or so.

Innovative programs are essential in today's norm and post pandemic period. Teachers and school leader's should continue to develop innovations as the pandemic taught us resiliency and readiness even in the most tough times. Embracing innovation would help us focus on the needs and crisis of our students, teachers would invite critical thinking skills as to the needs of their learners, and exploring new things that the students will eventually adapt to using and practicing in the classroom.

"Civilization can only move forward through innovation we should start innovation not in the university level, but in the basic education level," said Education Secretary Leonor Briones during the 2020 Innovation Forum: Innovation in Basic Education hosted by the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) at the PHIVOLCS Building, Diliman.

If innovation is being taught primarily at the basic education level, learners are considered to be confident and with a high level adaptability to change.

-END-